

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) AP_R13_H2N_Sq_Cyt_RT

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: AP_R13_H2N_Sq_Cyt_RT

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0071 A

Wavelength=0.71073

Cell: a=6.9269 (5)

b=7.7099 (6)

c=13.9934 (9)

alpha=92.495 (5)

beta=103.055 (6)

gamma=110.026 (5)

Temperature: 295 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	678.00 (9)	678.00 (9)
Space group	P 1	P 1
Hall group	P 1	P 1
Moiety formula	C15 H15 N3 O3	C15 H15 N3 O3
Sum formula	C15 H15 N3 O3	C15 H15 N3 O3
Mr	285.30	285.30
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.398	1.397
Z	2	2
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.100	0.100
F000	300.0	300.0
F000'	300.14	
h, k, lmax	9, 10, 19	9, 9, 18
Nref	7446 [3723]	6186
Tmin, Tmax	0.975, 0.987	0.965, 1.000
Tmin'	0.975	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.965 Tmax=1.000

AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 1.66/0.83

Theta(max)= 29.288

R(reflections)= 0.0543 (3886)

wR2(reflections)=
0.1114 (6186)

S = 1.020

Npar= 391

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level C**

STRVA01_ALERT_4_C Flack parameter is too small
 From the CIF: _refine_ls_abs_structure_Flack -1.700
 From the CIF: _refine_ls_abs_structure_Flack_su 1.000
PLAT340_ALERT_3_C Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds 0.00707 Ang.
PLAT915_ALERT_3_C No Flack x Check Done: Low Friedel Pair Coverage 79 %

● **Alert level G**

PLAT032_ALERT_4_G Std. Uncertainty on Flack Parameter Value High . 1.000 Report
PLAT720_ALERT_4_G Number of Unusual/Non-Standard Labels 6 Note
 H2BA H2BB H4BA H4BB H6BA H6BB
PLAT790_ALERT_4_G Centre of Gravity not Within Unit Cell: Resd. # 2 Note
 C15 H15 N3 O3
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C1A (Sohncke SpGr) R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C1B (Sohncke SpGr) R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C5A (Sohncke SpGr) R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C5B (Sohncke SpGr) R Verify
PLAT899_ALERT_4_G SHELXL2018 is Outdated and Succeeded by SHELXL 2019/3 Note
PLAT910_ALERT_3_G Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min). 1 Note
 0 0 1,
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600 393 Note
PLAT916_ALERT_2_G Hooft y and Flack x Parameter Values Differ by . 0.60 Check
PLAT941_ALERT_3_G Average HKL Measurement Multiplicity 3.3 Low
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value 1.914 Note
 Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 5.82 or SHELX Weight 10.92
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density. 1 Info

- 0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
3 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
14 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

- 0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
2 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
4 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
10 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
1 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check
-

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

